

Anonymisation plan – Qualitative research example

General information

Dataset name	Experiences of Psychology Students in Eastern Finland on Blended Learning 2013: Student Interviews
Creator(s) of the plan	Annika Sallinen
Responsible person	Maija Majava, Pentti Raccoon
Project summary	The interview was conducted with the help of interview themes that dealt with psychology students' experiences of blended learning at the University of Eastern Finland. In the interviews, questions were asked, for example: Have you been on courses that utilise blended learning, what are the good and bad things about blended learning, and how do you think the respondent learns best? No questions related to the respondent's social network or life course were asked in the interviews. At the beginning of the interview, the respondents were asked not to bring up the names of their loved ones, fellow students, or teachers.
Related sources	Additional information on respondents may be available from other sources of information, such as social media and Education Statistics Finland, using university and major subject information. In addition, if an intruder suspects that a person is studying at a university, he or she can check with the university's student affairs office if the person has given permission to hand over the name. It should also be noted that Master's and Doctoral theses are published openly online by name, year and major subject information.

Population and sampling

Population	<p>The population in the study consisted of all psychology major students present at the University of Eastern Finland in autumn 2013 (N: 273).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 139 students studying for a bachelor's degree, of which 16 are men. • 104 students studying for a master's degree, of which 12 are men. • 30 PhD's, of which 6 are men.
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Sampling	<p>The sampling is an overall sample and is self-selected. The interview invitation was sent to everyone by e-mail, and those who wanted to participate, participated in the study. The interviews were conducted as individual interviews and eventually 30 students participated. The participation rate is 11%.</p> <p>Interview participants N: 30</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 19 students studying for a bachelor's degree, of which 1 is a man. • 10 students studying for a master's degree, of which 1 is a man. • 1 PhD, of which 1 is a man.
Rare phenomenon	<p>When examining the gender of the respondents in the population, men are a minority among the respondents, as they make up only 34 of the 273 respondents, i.e. 12.5%. When looking at age, the rarest age groups in the population are those aged 15 to 19 (N: 3) and all age groups from the age of 40 onwards. The number of women in the light of age and degree data (bachelor's, master's, etc.) is reasonable in terms of anonymity, but men are rare observations in all age groups. For men, the largest age group consists of men aged 20 to 24 completing bachelor's studies (N: 8). Other age groups are equal to or smaller than 3. One rare combination of ages and degrees is men aged 40–44 with a doctorate degree, as there is only one of them in the target group. In the end, three men participated in the interview, two of whom are studying for a bachelor's or master's degree and one for a doctorate. The PhD belongs to the age group 40-44 and is a rare case, as previously.</p>

Dataset age

Age	<p>The data is young, as it was collected in the 2010s. It can be assumed that the respondents' information can be found on the Internet.</p>
Change over time	<p>It is unlikely that the information in the research data has changed significantly over time.</p>

Information value

Significant information	This study is interested in blended learning, especially how advanced the studies are and what their own learning methods are. Background information is particularly kept, i.e. information on the stage of studies and the degree to be completed. Other background information may be sacrificed for anonymisation. An examination by gender would be interesting in studies, but the small number of men may hinder the generalisability of the data.
Irrelevant information	Administrative direct identifiers are irrelevant for research purposes and can be removed or replaced.

Identifiers in the dataset

Identifier	Di ¹	In ²	Se ³	Decision whether to anonymise, chosen anonymisation technique and rationale ⁴
Personal names	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Replaced with invented first names. A personal name is often a direct identifier and must be removed. Here, the name is replaced by an invented name so that the characters can be matched within the same interview. University staff is categorised instead of named. Teachers and instructors are categorised, as they can be identified by gender alone if the gender distribution of instructors or staff is uneven. If the thesis supervisor is revealed, it also becomes easier to identify the student.
E-mail address	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. Direct and strong direct identifiers are always removed because they are easy to identify a person.

¹ Direct identifiers refer to Information that is sufficient on its own to identify an individual includes a person's full name, social security number, email address containing the personal name, and biometric identifiers (fingerprints, facial image, voice patterns, iris scan, hand geometry or manual signature).

² Indirect identifiers (or quasi-identifiers) are the kind of information that on their own are not enough to identify someone but, when linked with other available information, could be used to deduce the identity of a person. Background variables and indirect identifiers include, for instance, age, gender, education, status in employment, economic activity and occupational status, socio-economic status, household composition, income, marital status, mother tongue, ethnic background and place of work or study. Indirect identifiers relating to region of residence include, for example, postal code, neighbourhood, municipality, and major region. Date can also be an indirect identifier. Date of birth is the most common example, but dates of death and dates of newsworthy events may also be indirect identifiers in research data when combined with other information.

³ Sensitive identifiers contain categories of personal data specified in data protection legislation concerning racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religion or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health, sexual life or orientation, or genetic or biometric data for identifying a natural person. Other information may also be sensitive by nature. Sensitivity can be assessed by, for instance, considering whether the phenomenon is taboo or how much the disclosure of the information could provide harm to a person, organisation or other unit of observation.

⁴ Describe if you want to anonymise this identifier, what anonymisation technique you want to use and why this is a necessary and suitable anonymisation technique.

Gender	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. It was decided to completely exclude gender from the background data, as only three men are included in the data. Information indicating that the interviewee is a man will also be deleted. Gender comparisons with small data could remain unreliable from a research point of view, even though gender may play a role in blended learning.
Location	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. This information might be linked through information found on the internet.
Age	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Categorized [Under 30 years old] and [30 years old or over]. If precise information on age, doctoral degrees and gender were included in the data, background information could enable the identification of the person. Especially men and doctoral graduates can be identified by combining the data with other data.
Stage of studies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Categorized [Bachelor], [Master], [Doctoral student]. If precise information on age, doctoral degrees and gender were included in the data, background information could enable the identification of the person. Especially men and doctoral graduates can be identified by combining the data with other data.
Job positions or professional titles	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. This information might be linked through information found on the internet.
Attended courses	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The names of courses with a small number of participants, e.g. less than 20 and information on the content of the courses, if they identify the course, will be deleted.
Number of years of study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The number of years of study or the exact year of commencement of studies is classified every two to three years.
Previous study information	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed. This information might be linked through information found on the internet.

Other identifiable information

Open-ended responses	Where needed responses have been categorized, e.g. "Studying and working online are familiar from my work in [social services]." becomes "Studying and working online are familiar from my work [workplace]." Other responses have been verbalized, e.g. "There hasn't been enough energy for online learning at home because our daughter's knee problems required additional surgeries lately." Becomes "There has not been enough energy for online learning at home because [due to a reason related to children]."
Combinations	An external person may try to identify an individual person by combining data from the material with online thesis data and social media data (e.g. Facebook). The combined data may include, for example, the major subject of studies, university, year of commencement of studies, gender (in this case, especially male students) and information on the respondent's previous educational institution. The easiest group to identify are male students and especially male doctoral students, as their number among the target group is very small. The contact information of doctoral students can often also be found on the university's website. For the respondent's social networks, such as family members, friends, and teachers, it is easier to identify individuals, depending on what information the person has about the respondent. Fellow students or teachers are also potential downstream users of the material, so anonymisation aims to prevent identification also from persons close to the respondent's living environment.
Third persons	Names of thesis supervisors and fellow students who attended the same course. Identifying characteristics of these third persons have been deleted.
Future risks	People's knowledge of each other at the university must be considered, as future users of the material may be people working at the same university, even fellow students.